

ENERGY EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT MODEL AND CONTROL ALGORITHM FOR A ROBOTIC TECHNOLOGICAL IRRIGATION SYSTEM FOR AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. Today, the demand for water resources in agriculture is increasing day by day, but the drastic depletion of water resources and inefficient water losses in irrigation networks are leading to an increase in the demand for water. This article develops some proposals on how to achieve water saving and efficient use of technology through the use of innovative water-saving technologies in agriculture.

Key words: water shortage, drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, laser leveling, film drip irrigation, film tubular irrigation.

Introduction. It is known that, according to research by the World Natural Resources Institute and the British organization "Economist Intelligence Unit", by 2040, among the 33 countries that are expected to face water shortages the most, the countries of Central Asia, in particular the Republic of Uzbekistan, are the most unfortunate. This is a sign of the situation. This, in turn, is an important position for our home, located far from the ocean and large seas, no matter how established the assumptions are by this time. It must be said that a lot of work has been done in this regard in recent years in our country. Projects are being implemented in cooperation with leading countries of the world to introduce new and cost-effective technologies in the field of efficient use of water resources. Irrigation systems in agriculture include several components.

Here are some of the main components:

1. Electric Irrigation Machines: These machines are used for irrigation in agriculture. They help in powerful irrigation and provide water supply to the village.

2. Automatic control systems. These systems help automatically control irrigation machines. They work automatically and have settings to water at the right time.

3. Sensors and monitoring systems. These systems are used to monitor and manage water consumption in the village. With their help, water consumption and irrigation processes are monitored and automatically controlled.

4. Dehydration prevention systems. These systems help you use water efficiently, reduce water consumption, and prevent dehydration. These include safe and effective methods for efficient water use, water recycling and water conservation.

5. Renewable energy systems. Agricultural renewable energy systems, such as solar energy systems, can improve energy efficiency in rural areas. These systems reduce energy costs and reduce environmental problems.

Thus, agricultural irrigation systems include electric irrigation machines, automatic control systems, sensors and monitoring systems, drought prevention systems and energy resource utilization systems. These systems help effectively manage water consumption and improve energy efficiency in agriculture. The energy efficiency assessment model and control algorithm for a robotic technological irrigation system are very important for agriculture. To evaluate energy efficiency, it is necessary to examine the amount of energy used in the system's operating processes and the flow efficiency. For an assessment model, you can use sensors and monitoring tools to study the energy consumption and efficiency of each part of the system. Based on this information, you can create a model to calculate the overall energy efficiency of the system. Additionally, data analytics and data modeling will be important to study and optimize system performance.

A control algorithm is required to automatically control the system. The control algorithm controls the operation of the system, performs the necessary actions and settings, and determines the required amount of water. In this case, sensors, monitoring tools and an automated control system are important for the automatic operation of the system.

The control algorithm helps optimize system operation, minimize energy consumption and increase efficiency. This algorithm automatically manages monitoring and optimization processes and helps improve the efficiency of irrigation machines. The energy efficiency evaluation model and control algorithm of the robotic technological irrigation system for agriculture are of great importance to improve the efficiency and usability of the system. By creating these models and implementing a control algorithm, energy consumption and efficiency in agriculture can be improved, which will lead to increased activity and income.

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Thus, the goals of energy efficiency in an agricultural irrigation system are to reduce energy costs, provide convenience to consumers, protect nature, enhance production processes, and aid economic development. Thanks to these tasks, agriculture can increase its energy efficiency and develop qualitatively with economic benefits.

Energy efficiency of an agricultural irrigation system is important because these systems are composed of many devices and the efficiency of their production processes and activities depends on energy consumption. The energy efficiency of an agricultural irrigation system can be improved in the following ways:

1. Optimize energy consumption: It is important to determine and optimize how much energy should be used in production processes in irrigation systems. To optimize energy consumption, it is necessary to update technological processes, install automatic control systems, and use technologies that improve energy efficiency.

2. Reduce energy consumption. There are several ways to improve energy efficiency to reduce energy consumption in irrigation systems. For example, methods such as using energy-light devices and technologies, installing energy recycling systems, using light bulbs and sensors can be used.

3. Use of energy sources. The use of energy sources in agriculture such as solar energy, wind energy, hydropower and other alternative energy sources helps improve energy efficiency. The use of these resources will limit energy consumption in agriculture, and energy costs will be reduced.

4. Control and monitoring systems. It is important to install automated control and monitoring systems for irrigation systems. With the help of control systems, irrigation processes are optimized and energy efficiency is increased. Monitoring systems monitor the operation of irrigation systems and make necessary changes.

Thus, it is important to use technological innovation, optimize energy consumption and use alternative energy sources to improve the energy

efficiency of the agricultural irrigation system. Thanks to these ways, it is possible to increase energy efficiency in agriculture and reduce energy costs.

There are several important factors to evaluate the energy efficiency of a robotic irrigation system for agriculture. These factors are:

1. Energy consumption: How much energy a robotic irrigation system consumes, that is, what energy systems and devices operate in it, is an important factor.

2. Level of automation. The way automated tasks are performed using robots and sensors also impacts energy efficiency. Automated processes can improve energy efficiency.

3. Number of participants. The number of participants required in agricultural production processes also influences energy efficiency. Large numbers of participants may increase energy consumption.

And the control algorithm helps optimize energy consumption and control technological processes. These algorithms help optimize automatic systems to improve energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption. Control algorithms also play an important role in energy efficiency assessment.

Energy efficiency in agriculture, the importance of electric irrigation machines helps to minimize energy consumption in temporary irrigation processes. These machines extract water for irrigation and increase energy efficiency in these processes. Electric irrigation machines help in irrigation by pressing water and reduce water consumption in these processes.

Electric irrigation machines help effectively manage water consumption and improve energy efficiency in agriculture. Their operating methods and design are optimized to minimize energy consumption in irrigation processes. These machines are used for high pressure irrigation and reduce water consumption in these processes.

Electric irrigation machines play an important role in improving energy efficiency in agriculture. Their work together with automatic control systems, monitoring and sensors improves energy efficiency and allows efficient use of

water. Thus, electric irrigation machines are of great importance for improving energy efficiency in agriculture.

The automatic control system is very important for the energy efficiency of agricultural irrigation systems. The automatic control system controls the operation of irrigation machines and automatically determines the amount of water they need and the irrigation power. These systems are very effective in optimizing water consumption and minimizing energy consumption.

The automatic control system works in conjunction with the self-learning ability to control production, water consumption and irrigation processes. These systems are very useful in determining the amount of water required for industrial and irrigation processes where water consumption is high. Also, the automatic control system controls and optimizes water consumption, and also improves energy efficiency.

Automatic control systems help minimize energy consumption by automating the operation of irrigation machines and water consumption in agriculture. Their operation through monitoring and sensors improves energy efficiency and allows efficient use of water. Therefore, automatic control system is very important for energy efficiency in agriculture and is of great importance for efficient use.

Summary. Currently, our country uses 50-60 cubic km of water resources for the needs of various sectors of the economy. About 90 percent of these resources are used for agricultural purposes.

As a result of the project, it is expected that water savings will be 70%, the supply of water from irrigation canals to crops will increase from 37% to 90%, and the rational use of water will reach 97%.

It is planned to create a separate telemetry and remote control system SCADA based on new generation radio devices for operational monitoring and control of elements of the water supply network.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6024 "On approval of the concept of water management development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030". 10.06.2020

2. Decision PQ-144 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the introduction of water-saving technologies in agriculture". 01.03.2022.
3. Z.S. Shokhujueva, H.N. Mirjamilova. Innovative processes in the water sector and factors influencing their development. Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management. Том 12, №5, Стр. 18-27
4. N.S. Khushmatov, Z.S. Shoho'Jaeva. ASSESSMENT OF THE RELATIONSHIP OF WATER RESOURCES WITH THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL NETWORK. J.: Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. #3, Str. 1121-1129
5. Z.S. Shoho'Jaeva. FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN USING WATER-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES AND RESEARCH RESULTS OF THEIR RESEARCH IN AGRICULTURE OF OUR COUNTRY. J.: Oriental
6. З.С. Шохужева. Экономическая Эффективность Использования Инновационных Ирригационных Технологий. Журнал Экономика и социум. №6-2 (73). Стр.638-642
7. Тухтасин Нурмаматович Иминов. Приоритетные направления повышения эффективности ирригационных и мелиоративных. 2018.03.30, стр. 55-58.